

Replication package for "Towards LLM Accelerated Rapid Reviews for Software Tool Discovery - Case for Log Anomaly Detection"

Overview

An LLM agent (Claude) was used to automatically clone, install, and run 83 log anomaly detection repositories from GitHub. The agent used a 20-minute timeout per repository and selected the appropriate Python version (3.8–3.13) for each repo (~12 hours total).

Directory Structure

```
replication_package/
├── screening/                                # Screening results
│   ├── LLM_title_abs_eval.csv               # LLM screening of titles and abstracts
│   ├── manual_link_eval.csv                 # Manual evaluation of links for tools
│   └── validation.xlsx                       # Human evaluation of 386 title-abstracts
├── scripts/                                 # Scripts for the repository runner pipeline
│   ├── pipeline.py                          # Pipeline driver
│   ├── agent_prompt.md                      # LLM agent instructions
│   ├── run.sh                               # Bash wrapper with 20-min timeout
│   ├── repos_all.txt                        # Input repository URLs
│   └── generate_summary.py                  # Generates summary CSV from per-repo
├── results
│   └── plot_execution_times.py              # Generates execution time figure
├── prerun_results/                          # Pre-computed outputs from our run
│   ├── repositories/                       # Per-repo results (83 repos)
│   │   └── <repo_name>/
│   │       ├── action_plan.json            # Agent's install/run plan
│   │       ├── result.json                 # Outcome: success, grade, assessment
│   │       └── run_output.log              # stdout/stderr from execution
│   ├── logs/                               # Pipeline runner logs
│   ├── timings.csv                          # Per-repo timing data
│   ├── summary.csv                          # Aggregated results (83 repos)
│   ├── execution_times.pdf                 # Execution time distribution
│   └── execution_times.png
```

Note on script outputs: When you run the pipeline, scripts write to `scripts/repositories/`, `scripts/results/`, and `scripts/summary.csv` — separate from `prerun_results/`.

Grading Scale

Grade	Label	Description
3	Good	Installed and ran without issues
2	Usable	Ran successfully after minor agent intervention
1	Poor	Significant issues, partial or failed execution
0	Unusable	Could not run at all
NA	Timed out	Hit the time limit before completion

Per-Repository Artifacts

Each folder under `prerun_results/repositories/` contains three files:

- **action_plan.json**: The agent's assessment of whether the repository is runnable, which Python version to use, and the planned installation/execution steps. For non-runnable repos, contains a reason.
- **result.json**: The outcome including success status, installation grade (0–3), error messages if any, and a free-text assessment.
- **run_output.log**: Full stdout/stderr captured during the agent's installation and execution attempt.

How to Reproduce

Prerequisites

- Python 3.8+
- Claude Code (`claude`)
- Linux environment

Running the repository runner

```
cd scripts
bash run.sh
```

Note: Running requires Claude Code authorized with a Claude Pro subscription and takes approximately 12 hours. The LLM agent's behavior is non-deterministic, so exact grades may vary across runs.

Generating summaries from raw data

```
cd scripts

# Generate summary CSV from per-repo action_plan.json and result.json
python3 generate_summary.py

# Generate the execution time figure
python3 plot_execution_times.py
```

Summary CSV Columns

Column	Description
repo	Repository name
url	GitHub URL
runnable	Whether the agent deemed the repo runnable (True/False)
success	Execution outcome (True/False/Timeout/NA)
assessment	Free-text LLM assessment
error	Error message if failed
install_grade	Numeric grade (0-3 or NA)
install_grade_label	Human-readable grade label
python_version	Python version used
duration_seconds	Wall-clock time in seconds
exit_status	Process exit code